

THE IMPORTANCE OF "MENTAL ARITHMETIC" FOR PRIMARY STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article provides information on the importance of "Mental Arithmetic" for elementary school students.

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Keywords: digital economy, logic, imagination, analytical thinking, creative thinking, educational tool, negative numbers, talent, motivation, sum of numbers.

In recent years, great attention has been paid to the education system in our country. In particular, the fact that private schools were allowed to open and non-state educational institutions were allowed to operate freely led to the emergence of free competition in the education system. Naturally, where there is competition, research, striving for innovation, as a result of this research, high quality is achieved.

It became clear that it is necessary to introduce an innovative program, such as "Mental Arithmetic", which develops the thinking ability of students and strengthens their memory. Arithmetic (Latin Arithmos- number) is a science that studies numbers, operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication and division) given in sets of numbers. Examples and problems given with the help of numbers are solved in unique simple ways.

Mental arithmetic was first invented and implemented in China and Japan. Later it entered other countries. This program is a unique method of brain development based on children from 4 to 16 years of age counting in imagination with the help of an abacus, and the simultaneous rapid movement of the fingers of the right and left hands in harmony with the work of the right and left hemispheres of the brain. The following process occurs in the brain of a child engaged in mental arithmetic. In the process of performing a simple operation on the abacus, the left part of the brain is responsible for the execution of calculation operations in neurons, and the right part is responsible for motor skills, that is, it controls hand movements. The middle of the brain keeps the hearing of numbers under its control. For this reason, the right and left hemispheres of the brain work together in children engaged in mental arithmetic. Children engaged in this activity begin to master not only mathematics, but also other subjects. Their memory is strengthened.

There are several training manuals for teaching mental arithmetic, which are mainly developed based on the age of the child, that is, they become more complicated step by step. First, it is represented by various forms, and then numbers and formulas are reflected. For example: Arthur Benjamin and Michael Shermer's book "Secrets of Mental Arithmetic" is a clear example of this. Children engaged in the program of mental arithmetic develop the following abilities:

- Can concentrate;
- Ability to think creatively increases;
- Visual memory increases;
- Listening and observation are formed;
- Ability to read and understand improves;
- Can perform addition, subtraction, multiplication and division in imagination quickly, easily and accurately;
- Learns foreign languages well.

"Knowledge acquired in youth is like a pattern carved in stone." In the development and progress of every country, the place of the young generation with a bright future, thirsting for knowledge, is incomparable. Therefore, it is necessary to raise children from the age of preschool education in a spirit that is well-educated, in tune with the times, and able to confidently participate in the World Olympiads without losing their temper.

After all, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich is paying special attention to the education and future of the young generation. As an example of this, it is not for nothing that we have preschool educational institutions, Presidential schools, which are being built day by day and are becoming competitive with the world and have high-potential pedagogues. Nowadays, the young generation with high knowledge and memory like Alisher Navoi, Al-Khorazmi, Al-Beruni, who are imprinted in the pages of time, amaze us with their abilities. Even a 5-6-year-old child can't help but admire how he calculates mathematical examples in his mind like a calculator. You say it is not possible? Of course, there is a solution to every problem, so it is possible. "Mental Arithmetic", which came to us in recent years, develops attention, activity, and speed skills in students. As we live in the era of technological development and deep reform of the digital economy, we need to instill such qualities in every child for the next generation.

Mental arithmetic is an art, a mind-building program. With the help of this program, abilities such as achieving success in studying, creating life

motivations, being able to clearly set one's goals and moving forward are formed. What is mental arithmetic - although mental arithmetic has developed a lot in a short period of time, we still hear the same question from many people. What is "mental arithmetic"? An easy way to explain this is that if we consider any kind of sport, for example, in all of them, first of all, body training exercises are carried out, the athlete must have a physically ready form.

And regularly, athletes conduct such training exercises. Even champions are constantly working on maintaining their sports uniforms. Constant training and skills are the secret of a true champion. Even in the period of intellectual youth, the use of our brain is an important factor in achieving high results. For this, a set of effective exercises that develop brain activity is necessary. The main idea of mental arithmetic is to develop brain activity in children, develop abilities, and mature in the spirit of creativity. In short, mental arithmetic is a recognized type of mental gymnastics. Mental Arithmetic software teaches you to calculate mathematical operations in your brain faster than a calculator. It also creates wide opportunities for logic, imagination, analytical thinking and creative thinking in the child. This program has a very good effect on the development of brain activity of children aged 4 to 16 years. At this age, children's memory can perfectly store all lessons and news. The main teaching tool used in the program is an abacus. While working with this tool, our right and left fingers work equally, and the right and left hemispheres of our brain work equally. As a result, brain muscles are trained and quickly assimilate information. Six amazing benefits of abacus for children will increase the level of concentration. It is a quick calculation method that helps in calculation and arithmetic examples.

Accuracy is essential when calculating on an abacus. Simple arithmetic operations are easy to learn with the help of abacus. In addition, if children of preschool age are regularly engaged in mental arithmetic, during the school period, they will not have problems with understanding numbers, and this will greatly help children in mastering the basics of mathematics and other subjects. It increases the level of concentration in their daily activities. Not only this, it helps to develop better and faster computing skills. It is known that the brain has two hemispheres: right and left. The right hemisphere controls the left side of the body, and the left hemisphere controls the right side. In most people, the left hemisphere controls language and speech, while the right hemisphere controls nonverbal, creative abilities.

The method of imagining an abacus in the air in the way of imagination helps children to develop a visual representation of the problem in the brain. Through intensive training, it helps to increase the power of memory. When children calculate using an abacus, their hands, eyes and brain work together, they remember the actions shown in their brains and do not hesitate to accept the answer. After all, knowledge that is consistent with the times and firmly imparted is the foundation of high goals.

It was noted the importance of holding various contests among pupils, students and teachers in the subject of mathematics to motivate the winners, improving the Olympiad system and increasing the prizes given to the winners. It was said that it is necessary to raise the quality of teaching to a new level, to introduce a national certification system for the assessment of knowledge in mathematics. The holder of such a certificate is given the maximum score in mathematics when entering a higher educational institution. To increase the effectiveness of the system of training highly qualified pedagogues and personnel with scientific degrees. It was pointed out that it is necessary to give full independence to the scientific degree awarding council at the Institute of Mathematics. Also, the foundation stone of mathematics was laid by our great grandfathers such as Al-Khorazmi, Ahmad Farghani, Abu Rayhan Beruni. It's in our blood. Today, our goal in developing the science of mathematics is to create a competitive environment in mathematics, to train mature personnel in the fields of industry and engineering," said President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

According to experts, a student who has mastered mathematics well has a high level of analytical and logical thinking. Not only in solving examples and problems, but also in various situations in life, he develops the ability to quickly make decisions, conduct discussions and negotiations, and perform his work step by step. Mathematician's thinking takes him to the level of predicting future activities and events happening around him. After all, it is in the hands of us young people to take mathematics to a higher level. It is not for nothing that it is said: "Mathematics is a branch of science - be aware of its secrets."

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